

HTLV

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P071

Mycosis fungoides associated to HTLV-1 infection in a Peruvian cohort: a case series

Dr Francisco Bravo¹, Dr Francisco Conde¹, Dr Cesar Ramos^{2,1}, Dr Gabriela Garrido-Pinzás¹, Dr Cesar Salinas³, Dr Jaime Cok², Dr Fernando Mejía^{1,2}, Dr Carlos Seas^{1,2}, Dr. Eduardo Gotuzzo¹

¹Instituto de Medicina Tropical Alexander von Humboldt (IMTA VH)-Universidad Peruana Cayetano Heredia (UPCH), Lima, Peru. ²Hospital Nacional Cayetano Heredia, Lima, Peru. ³Clínica Cayetano Heredia, Lima, Peru

Background

The relationship between human T-lymphotropic virus type 1 (HTLV-1) and mycosis fungoides, a type of cutaneous T cell lymphoma remains obscure. While HTLV-1 infection has been closely associated to adult T cell lymphoma (ATLL), there is limited data on its relationship to other type cancers derived from the immune system such as Mycosis fungoides. Here we aim to present a retrospective case series of Peruvian patients with HTLV-1 infection who were also diagnosed with mycosis fungoides.

Method

We did a secondary data analysis to investigate the association of mycosis fungoides and HTLV-1 diagnosis on patients at the Hospital Nacional Cayetano Heredia and the Instituto de Medicina Tropical Alexander von Humboldt (IMTA VH) in Lima, Peru. Demographic information, clinical records, laboratory reports and biopsy reports (e.g., skin, bone marrow, ganglia). Current status was checked using national registers. We used descriptive statistics methods to obtain the results.

Results

We describe 26 patients with Mycosis fungoides and HTLV-1. Of these patients, 9 (35%) were male and 17 were female (65%). Regarding their ethnicity, 12 (46%) were mixed race, 11 (42%) were Andean, 1 (3%) was white, 1 (3%) was Asian and 1 (3%) unspecified. The median age at HTLV-1 infection diagnosis was 63 years (IQR 53 - 73.5) and the median age at mycosis fungoides diagnosis was 65 years (IQR 54 - 75). 8 of them (30%) are living, 16 (61%) are deceased and 2 were lost to follow-up. Additionally, regarding other HTLV 1-associated manifestations 6 patients (23%) had infective dermatitis, 1 (3%) had scabies and 1 (3%) had HTLV1- associated myelopathy/tropical spastic paraparesis (HAM/TSP).

Conclusion

Through this data we describe a possible association between HTLV-1 and Cutaneous T cell lymphoma/mycosis fungoides. This is a poorly recognized association, to our knowledge there are not many reports of these two entities. Further studies should be done in order to clarify the relationship

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between them. Additionally, we suggest that in countries with high prevalence of HTLV-1, patients with newly diagnosed Mycosis fungoides should be assessed for HTLV-1 as well.

Keywords

["Diagnostics";"Epidemiology";"Oncology, Other"]